

APPLICATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS TO THE RENEWAL OF TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY INFRASTRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: Based on their high strength- and stiffness-to-weight ratios, corrosion resistance, environmental durability and inherent tailorability, fiber reinforced polymer composites are being increasingly considered for use in infrastructure renewal. Areas of potential application, besides those involving composite cables and rebar, range from strengthening and seismic retrofit of reinforced concrete columns, decks and girders, to their use for all composite structural elements such as bridge decks. This paper explains the motivation and need for the development of composite systems for such applications and describes a number of such applications. The use of composites for the fabrication of light weight bridge decks that can be deployed in uses ranging from the replacement of deteriorating decks, to the erection of completely new superstructure is also described with test results. Aspects related to materials selection, manufacturing, quality control and standards for the use of composites in civil infrastructure are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: composites, civil infrastructure, renewal, decks, columns, seismic retrofit, durability, manufacturing.

INTRODUCTION

The deterioration of transportation related civil infrastructure represents one of the most significant challenges facing the nations of the world as we move our lifelines into the 21st century. The current impasse is due to the fact that (i) a large number of our bridge inventory are reaching the end of their initial design life, (ii) deterioration rates due to aging and environmental degradation are being accelerated and aggravated by causes ranging from poor initial construction and materials selection to shortcomings in design, workmanship and quality control and even improper use of retrofit and repair measures, and (iii) in addition routine maintenance has often not been conducted on these aging structures. Further, our traffic needs have increased dramatically over the past two decades with transportation of goods and services being conducted on a global, rather than local basis, resulting in a growing need for the widening of our highway system to accommodate more lanes, and for the renewal of existing structures to carry heavier loads at higher speeds. It is increasingly becoming apparent that deteriorating transportation related systems such as roads and bridges have a tremendous impact on society in terms of socio-economic losses resulting from delays and accidents. Anecdotal estimates point out that by 2005, traffic delays caused by an inadequate road system will cost the United States over \$50 billion a year in lost wages and wasted fuel. This will not only have an impact on local economies, but will in fact affect the economic well being of the nation in general.

Conventional materials such as steel, concrete and wood have a number of advantages, not the least among which is the relatively low cost of materials and construction. However, it is clear that conventional materials and technologies, although suitable in many cases and with a history of good applicability, lack in longevity in some cases, and in others are susceptible to rapid deterioration, emphasizing the need for better grades of these materials or newer technologies to supplement the conventional ones used. It should also be noted that in a number of cases, design alternatives are constrained by the current limitations of materials used, e.g. in the length of the clear span of a bridge due to weight constraints, or the size of a column due to restrictions on design and minimum cover needed. In a similar manner, often the use of conventional materials is either not possible in cases of retrofit, or may be deemed as ineffective in terms of functionality. In other case restraints such as dead load, restrict the widening of current structures, or the carriage of higher amounts of traffic over existing lifelines. In all such (and other) cases, there is a critical need for the use of new and emerging materials and technologies, with the end goal of facilitating functionality and efficiency.

Fiber reinforced composite materials, consisting of stiff and strong reinforcing fibers, held together by tough and environmentally durable resin systems show immense potential to add to the current palette of materials being used in civil infrastructure. Due to their high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios, corrosion- and fatigue-resistance, and overall durability, these materials are tailor made for use in infrastructure renewal. Despite the widespread use of fiber reinforced composites in the aerospace and defense related sectors, and the increasing potential for their use in civil infrastructure as showcased through demonstration projects, actual applications in the civil engineering sector have been slow. This is primarily due to three reasons: (i) unfamiliarity with composites, (ii) lack of predictive models, durability data, and design guidelines for their use in civil infrastructure, and (iii) economics related to fabrication. The key advantages of fiber reinforced composites, such as free-form and tailored design characteristics, strength/weight and stiffness/weight ratios which significantly exceed those of conventional civil engineering materials, high fatigue resistance, and a high degree of inertness to chemical and environmental factors, are often lost in high materials and manufacturing costs, particularly in direct comparison with conventional structural materials such as steel and concrete. However, the recent downturn in defense spending and the resulting need for new markets has spurred renewed efforts in reducing the costs of both raw materials and manufacturing processes, making it highly feasible to use composites in civil infrastructure. Within the vast applications area in civil infrastructure, this paper will concentrate on the narrow area of bridges, with focus on both rehabilitation and renewal. However, it should be mentioned that there is immense applicability in other areas such as tunnels, buildings, pipelines etc. We will also focus on the use of composites involving applications other than those using composite rebar, grids or cables.

APPLICATION IN THE REHABILITATION OF STRUCTURES

The use of composites for rehabilitation / retrofit / strengthening of bridge structures can be thought of as akin to the application of a surface layer that either protects and/or improves on the response of the encapsulated element. Within this area, three major structural areas can be identified (i) seismic retrofit of bridge columns, (ii) strengthening of deteriorated columns and piers, and (iii) strengthening of girders and bridge decks. Of these the first area has received perhaps the maximum attention because of the critical need for retrofit in areas of high seismic activity such as California and Japan as evidenced by the recent Northridge and Kobe earthquakes. Since topics in this area have been extensively discussed elsewhere, this section

will make brief note of advances in this area. Further discussion will be conducted in the section entitled "Issues Related to Materials and Manufacturability."

Seismic Retrofit of Bridge Columns

The confinement of concrete through the use of an external jacket has been proven to result in enhanced system ductility and subsequent performance under seismic events. This is because the external jacket provides constraint to the dilation of concrete in the absence of sufficient hoop steel. Amongst other conventional seismic retrofit strategies, steel jackets have been extensively used in both Japan and the United States. However this method of retrofit necessitates the welding of jacket sections in the field which is a concern as related to effectiveness and overall quality control. Further the use of steel in some areas carries with it the potential for rapid corrosion and degradation. The use of composites as wraps/jackets on columns to replace steel jackets in seismic retrofit has achieved a high level of interest both in Japan and the United States, with at least seven different methods being used to achieve the confinement of concrete, with the generic categories being listed below:

- Wet winding of tows,
- Winding of prepreg tow/tape,
- Wet layup of fabric,
- Layup of tape,
- Adhesive bonding of prefabricated shells,
- Insitu resin infusion of jackets, and
- Use of composite cables wrapped around concrete core

As an example of development, tests on 40% scale bridge columns at UCSD have shown that the use of carbon fiber reinforced jackets applied through the continuous winding of prepreg tow which is cured after completion of the jacket, can be as effective as steel jackets for retrofits in flexural lap splice and shear applications [1]. The advantages of such a method are (i) the fiber is continuously placed in the direction where it is the most efficient, i.e. the hoop direction and, (ii) the method of application lends itself to overall efficiency and quality control at a rapid rate of completion. An example of the dimensions and reinforcement layout of a shear column test specimen are shown in Fig. 1, emphasizing the small thickness of composite needed for retrofit.

Fig 1: Example Schematic Showing Retrofit Details for a Carbon Fiber Composite Jacket for Shear Retrofit

The dimensions of zones in Fig. 1(b) depict the changes in thickness possible over five zones, thereby enabling the efficient tailoring of composite thickness related to structural demand. For the column retrofit shown schematically in Fig. 1, stable hysteresis loops were obtained on testing up to a displacement ductility level of $\mu_{\Delta} = 10.5$. Comparisons with the as-built case (without retrofit) show a clear improvement in performance. Equivalent retrofit measures with steel jackets show a slightly increased initial stiffness and load carrying capacity with increasing ductility levels due to the isotropy of the material. It should be noted that both these aspects are in fact disadvantages since they result in the transmission of higher seismic forces to adjacent structural elements. The use of composites, especially as reinforced with carbon fibers in the hoop direction (providing directed confinement) thus provides a layup that is

Fig. 2: Rectangular Column Retrofitted Using Carbon/Epoxy Tow Preg and Subsequently Covered With a Protective Coating

tailored for the specifics of the application, providing materials efficiencies that were not possible with conventional materials. Extensive testing has been conducted using this technology with both 40% scale and full-scale validation tests. In addition successful field demonstration applications have been conducted on the I-10 Santa Monica Viaduct in Los Angeles and a comprehensive set of design guidelines have been developed [1,2]. The application of the technique to a rectangular column is shown in Fig. 2, wherein the entire jacket was coated with a layer that served both as protection and as an aesthetic coating. The use of composites in such an application has been shown to be cost-competitive with steel retrofits while providing the potential for faster fabrication with less lane closure and

potentially far greater durability over the life-time of use. Further details related to testing and materials selection are reported in [3] and discussed briefly in a later section

External Strengthening of Decks and Girders

*Fig. 3: Schematic Comparison of Placement of External Reinforcement
(a) Steel Plates, (b) Composite Plates*

The use of techniques associated with the external attachment of composite plates to the soffit of decks and the underside of beams for purposes of strengthening and retrofit is attractive due to factors related to ease of access and decreased need for extensive changes to the existing structure. Although the bonding of steel plates has been used extensively for over two decades, this method suffers from a number of disadvantages ranging from difficulty in placement, to concerns related to overall durability. Composite plates, on the other hand, do not suffer from most of these deficiencies, due to the high stiffness- and strength-to-weight ratios, corrosion resistance and light weight (Fig. 3). Beginning with the repair of the Ibach bridge in Switzerland, a number of retrofit and strengthening projects have been completed in Europe and Japan, along with a few demonstration projects in the United States. In recent years, this method has been used for the upgrading of bridge decks to enable the use of higher load levels such as in the case of the Hiyoshigura Viaduct in Chiba, Japan where two layers of carbon fiber unidirectional fabric were bonded to the underside of a deck section in order to increase capacity from a 20 ton level to a 25 ton level [4]. The use of composites in such applications provides yet another example of how light weight tailored materials can be used effectively to enhance and increase the life of existing civil infrastructure. Details related to use and testing of such applications can be found in [5,6].

REPLACEMENT BRIDGE DECKS

It is estimated that most bridges in the US on an average last 68 years, whereas their decks last 35 years, and that “during the 1990’s, 40% of the total highway deck area in the US will become 35 years old, statistically ready for replacement” [7]. Some estimates from the mid

west and from regions where there is extensive use of road salt, put the life of a conventional bridge deck at about 10 years, thereby requiring extensive triage, or expensive replacement within a short time period. States such as Wisconsin report that with the exclusion of painting, bridge deck repair and replacement accounts for between 75 and 90% of annual maintenance costs associated with the structure. Added to the problems of deterioration are the issues related to the need for higher load ratings (HS15 to HS20, for example) and increased number of lanes to accommodate the ever increasing traffic flow on major arteries. Beyond the costs and visible consequences associated with continuous retrofit and repair of such structural components are the real consequences related to losses in productivity and overall economies related to time and resources caused by delays and detours.

Reasons such as those listed above provide significant impetus for the development of new bridge decks out of materials that are durable, light and easy to install. Besides the potentially lower overall life-cycle costs (due to decreased maintenance requirements), decks fabricated from fiber reinforced composites would be significantly lighter, thereby affecting savings in substructure costs, enabling the use of higher live load levels in the case of replacement decks, and bringing forth the potential of longer unsupported spans and enhanced seismic resistance. There has been considerable activity over the past decade in the area of composite reinforcement for concrete bridges with the reinforcement ranging from composite rebar and grids to composite cables for external and internal post-tensioning. The current application, however, emphasizes the use of fiber reinforced composites for the entire deck or as part of the actual superstructure system itself. Such a concept, in general, is not new, having been used previously in the Miyun bridge in China and the Aberfeldy Footbridge in Scotland, among others. The focus of this section will be on developments in the area of replacement bridge decks capable of being placed on pre-existing concrete and steel girders, as well as being used in new bridge systems.

The overall test program was undertaken at the University of California, San Diego (UCSD) with funding from the Federal Highway Administration (FHWA), the Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA), and the California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) as part of a University-Industry Consortium, and was aimed at the development of lightweight, degradation resistant fiber reinforced composite decks for primary use in replacement. The overall criteria that were used to guide the development of these decks included: (i) the development of stiffnesses through the appropriate use of face sheets and internal core configurations that would fall in the range between the uncracked and cracked stiffness of existing reinforced concrete decks, (ii) the development of equivalent energy levels at acceptable displacement levels as a means of building in a safety factor due to the elastic behavior of composite sections, and (iii) the development of processing methods that would be cost-effective and which ensured repeatability and uniformity. A building block approach was used in this program with tests being conducted at the subcomponent, component and field-size levels as depicted in Fig. 4, so as to evaluate structural response, effect of fabric architecture and the effect of different core configurations, in components subject to shear and bending as appropriate. Components were fabricated by a number of industrial partners (as listed in Fig. 4) using Wet-Layup, Pultrusion, Resin-Infusion, and processes that were combinations thereof for manufacturing. Details related to these processes can be found in [8, 9]. In order to verify repeatability and uniformity between samples, a number of components were fabricated and tested to the same specifications as well. It was generally seen that structural response and failure modes could be replicated fairly uniformly.

CONFIGURATION	COMPONENT SCALE			
	3' - 4'	6' - 8'	14'	15' x 7.5' Panels
Balsa Core (Dupont)	●			
Foam Filled Boxes (Dupont)	●		●	
Foam Filled Truss (Dupont)	●	●	●	●
Foam Filled Hat Sections (Dupont)			●	●
Pultruded Profiles With Face Sheets (Lockheed-Martin)	●	●	●	
Hybrids (Lockheed-Martin)				●
Corrugated Core (Core-Kraft)		●		
"Egg Crate" Core (Northrop-Grumman)			●	

Fig. 4: Matrix of Test Specimens

Fig. 5 depicts sample test results from the subcomponent level tests. Each of these used a different core configuration in order to assess the effectiveness of various strategies. The truss core configuration consisted of triangular foam cores wrapped with fabric, which were assembled within face sheets to form the structure. In order to assess the effectiveness of additional reinforcement at the nodes formed by the adjacent triangles, the second configuration used a woven fabric insert that strengthened the node area. The effect of this on the overall ductility and performance of the system is clearly apparent, as response appears to shift from linear elastic to “pseudo-ductile” with the ductility being afforded by slow matrix cracking and gradual separation between fabric layers at internal nodes and along the inclined webs (Fig. 6). The use of such mechanisms could be considered as a means for arriving at pseudo-ductile response in structures and thus enabling gradual and non-catastrophic failure of primary load-carrying elements in a safety critical application. Larger component level tests were conducted on 14 ft long beams using a test setup that consisted of two high strength concrete abutments that were set at 8 ft centers in a hydrastone bed and post-tensioned to the test floor.

Fig. 5: : Load-displacement response of subcomponents tested in three-point bend mode

Fig. 6: Fabric Separation and Cracking at a Node

Continuity was provided on the cantilever end of the beam outside the supported span through the use of a structural steel yoke placed at the theoretical point of inflection of the adjacent span. The yoke was tied through the test floor. Each specimen was extensively strain gaged and deflection profiles were monitored using linear potentiometers. Examples of two such components are given in Figs 7 a and b.

Figure 7a: "Box" Type Component Showing Support and Loading Conditions

Figure 7b: Deformation of a Trapezoidal Core Component at a Load Level of 215 kips

The fiber reinforced composite deck specimens show failure loads far in excess of that shown by the reinforced concrete specimen with initial structural stiffnesses that are comparable. The "box" configuration and the "trapezoid" configuration also show significantly enhanced energy levels as can be seen from Fig. 8. Obviously further optimization is necessary in order to achieve the appropriate performance levels at the minimum cost. Costs are directly related to the thicknesses of composite used in the skins and in the webs formed with the core configuration. A concern often voiced about the use of fiber reinforced composites for primary structure is that related to brittle behavior and catastrophic failure. In most cases, the components showed considerable load carrying capacity and continued to carry load, albeit at significantly lower levels, even after substantial cracking and fracture were seen.

Fig. 8: Overall response of the 14 ft beam elements

— Reinforced Concrete	
— (#1) Truss Core (Resin Infused: All Glass)	62.15 kips/in
— (#2) Modified Hat Core (Wet-Layup: All Glass)	71.17 kips/in
— (#3) Modified Hat Core (Wet-Layup: Glass/Carbon Hybrid)	101.13 kips/in
— (#4) Modified Hat Core (Wet-Layup: Glass/Carbon Hybrid, Polymer Concrete Overlay)	104.78 kips/in

Fig. 9: Overall response of the field-scale deck panels

Further details related to strain and displacement response can be found in [10]. Field scale deck panels of size 15' x 7.5' x 9" were also tested for a limited number of concepts. These panels were fabricated in pairs, one each to be tested in the laboratory for assessment of stiffness and load-deflection response, and the other to be placed in a road test-bed for monitoring. Deck panels were fabricated following preset design criteria based on the achievement of a stiffness level between that of a cracked and uncracked concrete deck, and with the appropriate energy level to ensure safety. A panel using a glass/carbon hybrid construction was also tested, with and without a 0.75" polymer concrete overlay. All panels were approximately 8.25" thick, leaving 0.75" for the polymer concrete overlay. Panels were tested in the laboratory under simply supported end conditions with loads being introduced into the deck through two pads 6' apart and a spreader beam to approximate AASHTO HS loading conditions. Test results are shown in *Fig. 9*.

In each case, the composite decks were tested to a load of about 220 kips after which the test was terminated. It should be noted that the composite decks were 3 to 4 times lighter than the reinforced concrete deck panel which weighed about 12,500 lb., which translates into a threefold advantage, i.e. (a) lower deadweight enabling a higher live load capacity for the same supporting structure in cases of replacement decks, (b) lower dead weight enabling the use of lighter and smaller supporting- and sub-structure, in cases of new construction, and (c) lower dead weight enabling greater ease of field placement without heavy equipment.

4 deck panels (3 composite and one reinforced concrete) have been placed in a test site at UCSD in the road bed simply supported between two abutments 14 feet apart on centers traversing a hollow simulating a bridge. Deck-to-deck connections were made through the use of shear keys, backfilled with concrete. The site is on a heavily traveled road and hence affords the opportunity for field monitoring. The decks are instrumented with strain gages and linear potentiometers and response is monitored at regular intervals.

Fig. 10: Stages in the Placement of Composite Decks in a Road Test-Site

It is envisaged that monitoring will provide critical information on the actual behavior of these decks under actual traffic conditions. *Fig. 10* shows the placement of decks in the test site using fork-lifts, which emphasizes the immense advantage of lighter weight vis-à-vis field placement. This will also translate to faster completion of projects, thereby reducing time of road closures.

CONCEPTS FOR RENEWAL / NEW STRUCTURES

Although the areas of rehabilitation and retrofit offer the maximum potential for immediate application of composites in civil infrastructure, the development of new systems that combine the directionality and high performance levels of composites with the dominant characteristics of conventional materials (such as with concrete in compression) show great potential for advances in the design and construction of new civil engineering structures. One such concept is that of composite shell systems for columns, wherein prefabricated composite tubes serve the dual purposes of form-work and reinforcement, thereby replacing the reinforcing steel while enabling faster construction. In this system, the column is constructed by placing the hollow composite shell in place, and then filling it with concrete, without any steel along the height of the column. Construction details are such that it can be directly incorporated with conventional construction methods. Fig. 11 shows such a system being tested, whereas Fig. 12 depicts a section with the shell removed showing the use of ribs in the composite shell to enable continuity of deformation and stress transfer between the shell and the concrete encapsulated by the shell.

Fig. 11: Composite Shell System

Fig. 12: Cut-Away of the Composite Shell System Showing the Shell, Ribs and Encapsulated Concrete

The composite shell system has been successfully tested using two concepts: (a) wherein starter bars from the footing extended into the column providing a conventional anchorage mechanism into the footing and/or bridge superstructure, and (b) wherein steel is completely eliminated with anchorage force mechanisms consisting of the reaction moment due to the compression force couple generated inside the footing and the frictional stresses between the composite shell and concrete [11]. The initial success of this system has led to the development of a complete bridge system, wherein the girders and columns are fabricated from composite shells [12]. An example is shown in Fig. 13a for a space truss bridge, whereas Fig. 13b depicts a concept for a dual tied arch bridge where the arches are comprised

of concrete filled carbon fiber reinforced tube segments and the tie girders are similar tubes which are post-tensioned. Cross-beams are connected to the tie girders using a Lincoln log system with joints being filled with concrete.

Fig. 13: Concepts for Modular Composite Shell Bridge Systems (after [12])

ISSUES RELATED TO MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURABILITY

The ultimate success of the applications described in the previous sections, as well as others being developed across the world will be dependent on the appropriate selection of materials and manufacturing methods that will enable these applications to live up to their full potential. The use of composites in civil infrastructure is different from its use in applications in the aerospace arena for a variety of reasons including (a) decreased need for very high dimensional control, (b) increased need for uniformity and standardization, even at the cost of some loss in tailorability, (c) increased need for materials that are capable of withstanding a severe environment (nature) over long periods of time with very little in-depth inspection, and a minimal amount of maintenance, and (d) increased emphasis on cost. This does not mean that civil structures will not be inspected at routine intervals, but it should be understood that the inspections will take place in the field, in conditions that may be far from ideal due to the vagaries of climate, and component position. This predicates that not all routine aerospace based NDE techniques will be viable. Also the overall safety of these structures is of paramount concern and hence materials selection and the determination of design values for characteristics of performance is very important.

The selection of a composite materials system for use in civil infrastructure needs to be predicated on the requirements of both short- and long-term performance, as well as on the

environment in which the performance is required. Although it may be tempting to choose the fiber reinforcement primarily on the basis of cost or stiffness, and the resin on the basis of cost or toughness, it is imperative that both be chosen on the basis of a number of factors including: (a) cost, (b) structural performance in terms of strength and/or stiffness, (c) damage resistance in terms of factors such as impact resistance and toughness, (d) resistance to environmental degradation and deterioration especially from aspects such as moisture, heat, freeze-thaw and alkalinity, (e) long-term performance factors such as creep and relaxation, and (f) manufacturability, including the effect of adverse field conditions on in-process defect formation. It is also important to differentiate between those applications which are stress critical, from those that are driven by the modulus of the material, and even those in which performance may be dependent, at least in part, on levels of failure strain (e.g. seismic retrofit of columns needing plastic hinge confinement).

Although some bare fibers, such as glass, may be rapidly affected by environmental factors, the degradation is significantly retarded or even nullified by the selection and application of the appropriate sizing and resin system. The engineer thus must consider the resin system not just as a medium that holds fibers together and serves as a basis for shear transfer, but also as a protective layer over the fibers themselves. Generically, a designer could consider polyesters, vinylesters and epoxies as the building block matrices for composites used for civil infrastructure applications. Of these the polyester systems are the simplest and the most economical. Orthophthalic polyesters should be avoided wherever possible since they have limited thermal stability and chemical resistance. Isopolyesters have better performance characteristics and have increased resistance to water permeation. Vinylester resins have characteristics similar to those of the Isopolyesters but often have better environmental resistance especially when used with glass fibers wherein interfacial bonding is better than with the isopolyesters. However, these resins do not bond as well to carbon fibers because of the lack of sizings that are compatible with them, resulting in decreases in shear and compressive properties. Epoxies are generically the most expensive of the three types of systems, but show the best overall performance and the least shrinkage upon cure. A number of blends are now available that combine the best characteristics of the systems and offer very good resistance to moisture penetration. The application of a gel coat or a resin-rich surface layer is also recommended for most applications using glass fibers as the reinforcing phase so as to provide a further barrier between the environment and the reinforcing fiber. Although considerable data exists for the environmental resistance of aerospace grade composites, data is not readily available for composites used in civil infrastructure. Degradation to these composites, when it occurs, usually affects strength, rather than stiffness, and hence care should be taken to apply strength reduction coefficients to designs to account for drop-offs in short-term and long-term performance levels. Table 1 gives a conservative estimate of time dependent strength reduction coefficients for E-glass, S2-glass, and carbon fiber reinforced composites.

Table 1: Strength Reduction Coefficients

Characteristic	E-Glass Composites	S2-Glass Composites	Carbon Fiber Composites
Short-Term	0.6-0.7	0.7-0.8	0.95
Long-Term	0.25-0.4	0.3-0.5	0.9

In each case, however, these should serve as guidelines only, with the actual factors being determined as far as possible taking into account the specifics of the materials systems used

and the requirements and loading regime associated with the application. Similar to the reduction factors used for short- and long-term performance on the basis of strength, factors need to be determined as related to fatigue and creep strength associated reduction. These obviously depend on the type of constituents chosen, and also on the form of the reinforcement used.

Table 2 gives an example of fatigue and creep strength reduction coefficients for E-glass reinforced composites. The table, again, serves as an example, underlying the critical need for the development of a good data base on materials to be used in civil infrastructure applications, along with the determination of appropriate materials related factors for design. Guidelines such as those given in Tables 2 and 3 should be used appropriately, keeping in mind that materials should not be blindly discarded because of the factors, since in a number of cases, the actual loading regime may not be affected significantly by the reduction coefficients (e.g. in some applications designs could call for the use of thicknesses of face sheets in order to meet stiffness or deflection critical criteria, resulting in very low stress levels even under overload conditions, which would mean that the material could still easily meet all long-term strength and creep-rupture requirements).

Table 2: Fatigue and Creep Strength Reduction Coefficients

Condition	E-glass Continuous Strand Mat in Polyester	E-glass Woven Roving in Isopolyester	Unidirectional E-glass/Epoxy
<i>Fatigue Stress Ratio</i>			
10 ³ cycles	0.5-0.65	0.3-0.45	0.4-0.6
10 ⁶ cycles	0.25-0.4	0.2-0.35	0.2-0.35
<i>Creep Rupture Stress Ratio</i>			
1000 hours	0.4-0.65	0.55-0.65	0.7-0.85

Often designs have to be developed based on limited data, or data that is deemed to be “representative” of the materials to be used. The question then arises as to what levels should be used for preliminary design allowables. Although the actual resolution of the question depends on the interplay between the manufacturing method used and degree of quality control (both of the incoming raw material stream and the finished product), reasonable values of strength allowables can be estimated through the use of one of the procedures in Table 3.

Table 3: Approximations for Strength Design Allowables

Procedure	Design Allowable
Nominal	Average - 3(Standard Deviation)
A Basis	50% of Average
B Basis	75% of Average

The selection of materials is also predicated by the specifics of the application itself. In applications where a composite is externally bonded to a concrete surface for the purposes of

strengthening, the efficiency of the measure will in large measure be dependent on the efficacy of the bond between the composite and the concrete substrate.

Fig. 14: Systems Level Interactions

An aspect that needs to be kept in mind during the design of such schemes is that related to the long-term environmental durability of the composite, and the durability and effectiveness of the adhesive bond between concrete and the composite. Adhesion and bond between the two are aspects that need to be looked at very closely not just because of the mechanics of rehabilitation, but also because of the influences of a variety of variables, external and internal on the response of the system (Fig. 14). It is important to remember that the strength and effectiveness of assemblies depends largely on the cohesive strength of the adhesive and the degree of adhesion between the two adherends. Of equal importance to the efficiency of the adhesive is the method of surface pretreatment of the adherends prior to the application of the adhesive. Most engineers tend to focus on the achievement of a prescribed initial bond strength but it must be noted that although important, this metric is not as important as that of bond durability as dictated by the environmental stability of the adherend-adhesive interface. This is especially true of assemblies that are subjected to the vagaries of nature, including extremes of temperatures (often within a 24 hour cycle), moisture, sustained and cyclic loading. Further details related to these aspects are reported in [6,13].

Fig. 15: Comparison of Failure Modes as a Consequence of Environmental Exposure to (a) Fresh Water Under Ambient Conditions, (b) 0° F (dry)

The use of composites in the strengthening of columns and in seismic retrofit calls for the use of reinforcement predominantly in the hoop direction. This is a fiber dominated application, with the predominant role of the composite being to enable the application of constraint to the concrete core. Although the resin then may appear to be extraneous, it serves a very useful function beyond that of a matrix in acting as a protective layer for the fibers, both from environmentally induced and accidental impact induced damage. It should however be noted that the composite, even in the undamaged state, changes response to a certain degree with the environment. A classic example is that of increase in stiffness and compression strength after exposure to 0° F (dry) temperatures due to matrix hardening. Not only can this change the response of the entire system (stiffness changes can be as high as 15-20%) but it also results in the introduction of new forms of damage and failure mechanisms. *Figs. 15a and b* show the dramatic change in failure mode of a glass epoxy wrap after short-term exposure to fresh water (at ambient temperature) and 0° F (dry) conditions. The tearing, inter-roving delamination and shredding of the hoop reinforcement in the former is traceable to the enhanced stiffness and hardening of the resin at sub-zero temperatures. Effects such as this, although not dangerous in a structural sense, do need to be taken into account during design. Effects of environmental exposure on the response of such systems are further elucidated in [14,15].

A common concern related to the use of fiber reinforced composites in civil infrastructure is the accurate determination of composite properties that can directly be used by the designer. A specific example of this is in the area of seismic retrofit where composite properties are needed for materials used in the confining jacket under loading conditions that replicate the actual situation of a confined column. Coupon level tension, flexure and shear tests which are routinely conducted to characterize composite properties do not address this important aspect. One way to determine properties which simulate those in a field wrap is to conduct a NOL ring or "burst" test, wherein a 20" diameter ring of the material in the configuration used in a jacket is placed in an apparatus and then hydraulically pressurized internally to simulate confinement and impart only circumferential stresses to the ring. An added advantage to such a test, beyond the determination of design properties, is the capability to test systems that are fabricated through the adhesive bonding of shell segments to form a jacket. Whereas tensile, or other characterization level tests would not give a true indication of structural performance, and failure mode, the NOL ring test does, even replicating failure initiation. This test can also

be used to accurately assess the effect of environmental exposure on the behavior of the retrofit system itself, including that induced by premature softening or plasticization of the adhesive, if any. It is strongly recommended that special efforts be made by the composites community to develop simple tests such as the NOL test which provide data to the civil engineering designer directly combining materials aspects with those of structural form and manufacturing.

Although the tests conducted to date on fiber reinforced composite decks have shown that they can be fabricated using a variety of processes with performance levels based on quasi-static testing that are acceptable for use in replacement strategies, a number of issues still need to be investigated before the actual implementation of such decks in the field. Some of these issues relate to response under dynamic loads, long-term durability of materials, connections between the decks and supporting girders, and connections between the decks and barriers and side rails. Due to the plethora of choices available in fiber and resin types, fabric architectures and processing methods, it is critical that specifications be developed based on performance standards, not just at the materials level, but also at the component and systems level. These standards must necessarily include recommendations on partial safety factors to accommodate variations due to differences in raw materials, quality achievable through different manufacturing processes, durability based on material choices and bridge environment, structural response and damage. It is highly probable that such deck systems will interact with pre-existing or new structural components fabricated from conventional materials and it is critical that interface issues as related to coefficients of thermal expansion, residual stresses and moduli differences are resolved without adversely affecting overall systems response. Issues such as cost-effectiveness and overall manufacturability must be addressed in the near future if such schemes are to compete with conventional strategies. It must be noted that overall cost-effectiveness is intrinsically tied to the degree of efficiency in materials conversion through the choice of a manufacturing process or processes. It is conceivable that future directions will emphasize the use of hybrid construction, encompassing not just hybrids of different reinforcing fibers, but also hybrids combining fiber reinforced composites with conventional materials such as steel and concrete. Future development in deck systems will have to consider a systems level approach based on the specifics of the application under consideration.

CONCLUSIONS

Fiber reinforced composites provide an immense palette of opportunity for the civil engineer to combine form and function in a manner not possible to date, and hence open up new vistas for the development of methods for renewal, including those involving new structural systems. Demonstrations and applications have clearly shown that these materials will be applied in future projects. However the extent of these applications will depend in large part on the resolution of outstanding critical issues that include (a) durability and fire protection, (b) reparability of composite structural elements, (c) development of validated codes, standards and guidelines of use to the civil engineering community, (d) development of cost-effective design approaches and manufacturing methods, and (e) provision of an appropriate level of quality assurance and control both during manufacturing and installation using unskilled construction labor.

Future developments in this area will probably emphasize hybrid construction wherein the most efficient aspects of composites are combined with dominant properties of conventional materials to provide the best overall structural response. It is already feasible that this technology will enable the construction of longer span bridges which meld in with the surrounding environment, providing exceptional structural response along with outstanding aesthetic features.

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